

Civic Amenities and Characteristics among Small Urban Towns in India: A Case Study of Kushinagar

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Abstract-

In India, from very beginning the concentration of development is mainly taking place in Metros or class 1 cities as compared to the small and medium size towns. The small urban centers can provide a better ground for the modern urbanization have become the victim of serious problems and therefore unable to play a proper role in the context of socio-economic world. In fact, the challenges of urbanization are badly affected due to this urban poverty which is largely an extension of rural poverty. Thus, in the context of development, if these centers are provided with proper provision of urban facilities along with employment, education, urban amenities and social protection which attract the rural people and fulfill the rural needs. With this view, the present paper try to study the position of infrastructural facilities like water supply, sanitation, electric, telecommunication, education, health, recreation, shops, road and transport in small urban centers of Kushinagar, which is the district of middle Ganga Valley and one of the most populous region of India.

Keywords; small urban centers, urbanization, urban amenities, infrastructure.

Introduction:

Some empirical studies suggest a strong relationship btw infrastructure and economic growth. According to the 'world bank' 1% increase in infrastructure is associated with a 1% increase in GDP across all countries. A study by Deichmann (2002) for Mexico shows that a 10% increase in market access leads to a 6% increase in labor productivity. Broadly speaking, the development of infrastructure has five fold impact on the economy: Creating access to employment and providing future earning opportunities. Creating access to previously inaccessible commodities and services. Increasing production efficiency. Saving time, which can be better utilised in productive activities. Improving the health and physical condition of the population. Study Area With this view, in the present paper, tried to study the condition of urban facilities of Kushinagar district, one of the small urban centres of India. Kushinagar is the district of middle Ganga valley, which is one of the most populous regions of India. It is lying $26^{\circ}38' - 27^{\circ}18' N$ and $83^{\circ}33' E$ to $84^{\circ}36' E$ on the eastern

margin of Uttar Pradesh, covers an area of 2906 sq. km, which linked by N.H.28 and Gorakhpur-Kaptanganj railway line. Land resource is the base of economy. 76.3% area of district under agriculturally productive land or cultivated. The district consist of four tehsils, 14 development blocks, 141 Nyay Panchayat, 1560 villages, 957 Gram Panchayat and 7 urban centres, namely Padarauna Nagar Palika, Khadda, Ramkola, Severahi, Kasia, Hata, Kaptanganj are six nagar panchayat according to census 2001. Total population of urban centres are 132523 in 2001 and 170385 in 2011 which is 4.58% and 4.78% of district population. In the study area, there is a lack of proper infrastructure of Kushinagar, where majority of rural population i.e. 95.13% of total population. They are neither eager nor conscious towards the development of these activities. In urban centres, the development of amenities is also slow due to lack of proper attention and poor investment by the town development authorities. Table (1) reveals the development of infrastructure in the small urban centres of Kushinagar btw 1991 to 2011 decade.

Water And Sanitation-

In the rural areas of Kushinagar hand pumps are the main source of drinking water. In each village four to five hand pumps have been installed by government. From earlier seven urban centers are also being served by tube wells and water taps. But these sources only function a few hours a day, however, because of poor maintenance. Water supply is found inadequate especially during summers when the suffering is more due to increasing demand of water by the inhabitants. Despite the impressive coverage of provision of safe drinking water, there is a great deal of concern about both quality and sustainability. At several places supply pipes are cracked and are near some dirty areas. At a few places the sewer pipes are close to the drinking water pipes. Most of the hand pumps in such area are not so safe as they mostly have a depth of 80 feet's only, which contains a lot of pollutants that have reached the underground water. In Kushinagar, there are calcium and sulphate are most common constituent causing hardness of natural water. Due to the imbalances of mineral salts, deficiency diseases like thyroidal problems are common and also causing epidemic problems are common in this area. In this regard, India mark hand pipes have been provided by government within the area. Except Padarauna all the centers suffer from these conditions of water supply. In the Padarauna more than 70% households use the water taps, 10% Hand pumps and 15% household have no proper supply; they depend only on nearby India mark hand pumps. In Saverahi and Khadda only 40% houses have water taps, 30% houses have no proper provision of water supply. (Table: 2)

The situation of sanitation is rather dismal. Survey indicated that with less than 50% of households having functional latrines in Khadda and Saverahi. In Kasia and Padarauna 66% households have their own functional latrines. While in Ramkola, Kaptanganj and Hata have 50 to 60% households with latrines.

The government subsidizes the building of latrines by households that are below the poverty line, governments share the subsidy to households for constructing latrines which is about 80% of the unit cost. Despite these incentives people are slow to adopt sanitation practices.

Power, Telecommunication & Recreation:

Although the power supply available but these centers are always suffering from frequently power cuts and electric faults. Till 1971 all the centers linked with electric power but Kasia and Padarauna have proper power

supply. While in Ramkola, Kaptanganj, Saverahi, Hata and Khadda, there are 10 hours in day or night power supply in alternate weeks and also have no regular supply. They are always suffering from frequent power cuts, low voltage supply and electric faults. There is also a big problem of unauthorized use of the electric current. Nearly 40% of households have Katia system. This system is very harmful and sometimes gives a very strong spark. The available total telephone connections in urban areas were 1113 in 1991, which is 4187 in 2001 and 1488 in 2011. The above figures reflect the trend of development in using mobile phones instead of landline telephones because it is easy to handle and portable. Table I shows the highest figure in Padarauna. In Khadda, there is only 231 connections in 2001 and 56 in 2011 less than other centers. 261 public call offices (2011) in urban areas, in which 64 in Padarauna, 25 in Hata, 52 in Saverahi, 26 in Kasia, 30 in Kaptanganj, 24 in Ramkola and 40 in Khadda. This figure is very low in 1991, only 92 public call offices in entire region. In 1981 there is only one Targhar in each urban centers accepting Kasia but in 2001, Targhar of Kasia, Ramkola, Kaptanganj and Khadda were closed only four Targhar are in urban area of Kushinagar. But these are closed now. All centers are provided postal services. In 1981, there were 10 post offices in urban centers, in which 4 in Padarauna, 2 P.O. in Kasia one in each other urban centers but in Kaptanganj, there was no any Post office. Now one P.O. is open in Kaptanganj. In present, there is 4 post offices in Padarauna, 2 in Kasia and 1 in each other urban centers. In 30 years, there is no development shows these figures because the negligence of these small urban centers. Healthy urban recreations like cinema houses are there, like- there are two cinema house in Kasia out of which only one is running properly, same condition is in Padarauna, here are three cinemahouses but only two are running properly; But In Hata & kaptanganj there are one cinema house each but these are closed now a days; these cinema houses are not working properly due to their local disputes, lack of purchasing power of people, lack of facilities etc; but here is no park or any play grounds. In the whole area only 'Buddha Nirvan Sthal' in Kushinagar is develop as a recreation Centre due to its tourism importance. Not only this, the point of worry is rather stagnation of many of the small towns of India. In these centers the surrounding villagers visit for having a change from their routine life and have a pastime.

Health & Educational Services:

The conditions of medical facilities are not so good. There is one district hospital in Kasia, Hata & Padarauna. Except Sevarahi and khadda, there is one Community Health Centre (CHC) in each other five urban centers. From 1981 there exist four primary health centers in urban centers. In present; there is 3 PHC in Padarauna and one PHC in each six urban centers. But sufficient beds, O.T. and specialist doctors are not available as required and those who are available are in poor condition. There are 5 Aurvedic hospitals, in which 2 are in Padarauna, 1 is in Kasia, Hata and Kaptanganj each. 8 homeopathic hospitals or clinic in entire area where no single doctor is available, in the absence of doctors the hospitals are closed for whole day. The family planning and mother child welfare centers are allotted one to each urban centers with the work load of surrounding areas. Private clinics are in much better position but their fee is very high, In order to avail the advance specialized and emergency medical facilities available in these hospitals (TABLE-3).

As for as the educational facilities are concerned the changes have molted to a considerable extent. In 1981 seventeen junior school, thirteen higher secondary, nine senior secondary school three degree collages were present in Kushinagar urban area. In which Padarauna ranked first in no of institutions and Kasia was second. With increasing population and demand some junior, higher and secondary schools are also open but they are not sufficient for extra opportunity and their services are not satisfactory. In present, 28 junior basic school 24 senior basic school 34 higher secondary school and 28 P. G. colleges in 2011. There are more than 100 Montessori nursery schools are open throughout the urban area which influence the modern education (Table: 4). But above all, it is clear fact that the school and colleges spread in a greater number but more of them are away from quality contents and fulfill the need of present day race. Also the condition of higher education is not satisfactory only four P.G. collages (Financed) are in Padarauna, Kasia, Saverahi & Fazilnagar each from 1981, who have the responsibility to shape the youngsters future with their traditional education which is insufficient without any professional assistance. After 2005, there are 26 self-finance collages are also present in these areas but they don't provide quality education; there are a few private technical/vocational training centers as in table (4), but they are not up to the standard to make students future secure; neither these institution

are able to fulfill the needs of local people as for as neighboring rural people. No doubt, these institutions behave as a factory of degrees.

Other Institution:

These types of institutions are too busy to perform as a base for collection and subsequent distribution of agricultural products of the surrounding region. It is actually this rural based function which link small towns with the country side. These are banks, polish station, control rate shop, cold storage, godowns, agricultural and animal service Centre, clothe shop, gold & silver shops, cycle sell & repair shop, hardware shops, book & stationary shops, Aurvadic, medical drugs, Tractor and agricultural implement sell and repair are Centre place function available generally in small towns. Table (5) reveals that the developments of this type of shops are very slow between two decades (1991-2001). There is only one polish station in each urban Centre in 1991 and same in 2011. Control rate shops are 38 in 1991 and 70 in 2011, in which 27 shops in Padarauna, 8 in Kasia & Saverahi each, 8 in Hata & 5 in Khadda, 6 in Ramkola and 5 in Kaptanganj. Being large rural centers six cold storage are provide here two in Padarauna two in Kasia and Ramkola & Sevarahi have one cold storage each, but it's astonishing that out of six, only laree cold storage Kasia is running rest 5 are closed. There were 22 seeds and pesticides centers in 1981 which is now 67. From 1981 to 1991 there were no single agricultural service centers, but in 1995 agricultural service centers were opened and now it is 84 in 2001 and 70 in 2011. These agro based urban centers got only 10 cooperative societies out of which 6 are in Padarauna & Sevarahi, Kasia; Ramkola & Hata has one each. Table (6) shows the banking position of entire region there were 12 branches of nationalized bank in 1981 which were 23 in 2011, in which 5 are in Padarauna, 5 in Kasia, 3 in Ramkola, Kaptanganj, Hata and 2 in rest two urban centers Sevarahi & Khadda. All seven centers have 1 branch of Gramin Bank, 2 branches of corporate bank in Padarauna while other six centers have one branch each. But now 4 branches are closed. There are three branches of Bhumi Vikash bank in urban area in which 1 in Padarauna, Kasia and Hata each. Different type of shops like pan shops, clothe, gold & silver, book & stationary, cycle sell & repair, medicine, bakery, provision stores, country liquor, utensil, fruit and vegetable shops are present in these centers. But only Padarauna, Kasia and Hata have manyshops which fulfill the needs of rural centers also. Ramkola, Kaptanganj, Khadda and

Saverahi have no sufficient shops that fulfill the needs of rural people beside these centers. The people of these centers are come in other urban centers.

Road and Transport:

Small towns and roads are closely associated and contribute to each other development by virtue of their intrinsic qualities of functions. The study area is well served with a good network of transport arteries. National Highway (N.H. 28) travel from Kasia, Hata and Saverahi which is now known as east-west corridor, beside this all other local metaled and non-metaled roads which are provide a great impetus for the development of urban centers connected with district headquarter. All the centers are connected with each other but around 50% villages of countryside are not connected to road network. The total available roads in these urban centers are 180 Km.long in which only 60 Km. length is metaled, according to statistics of Kushinagar 2013. In Padarauna a state roadways depot is under construction. Many state transport bushes and undertaking bushes are running up and private bushes & taxies are also running between these centers and other centers also. Authorized bus services are available from Padarauna & Sevarahi, Kasia is in center because of that these buses passes through it, as well as Hata is on the way to Gorakhpur so that buses are available from there too. But from Ramkola, Khadda & Kaptanganj there is no such authorized bus facility available, people are bound to use private transport like-Taxi, mini bus etc

Conclusion:

Our study of small urban center's infrastructure for housing, electricity, water, sanitation, telecommunication, road and transport reveals many common themes and common problems across the sectors. First is the fundamental importance of access to basic infrastructure for productivity, improving quality of life and stimulating economic development. And second, unfortunately, is the lack of such access in all sectors, because urban services are ignored by town development authority. The scenario of urban facilities is not properly developed for providing good life style and economic development. They are suffering from highly negligence of development. Although this infrastructure includes a number of capital assets for different provisions but these assets have suffered from poor maintenance and little attention, has been paid to the quality of service actually delivered. On the basis of my study, I can say that the existing infrastructure of

services and community facilities of small urban centers have become outmoded, due to over population density. More than half of the people suffer from bad, unsafe and unhygienic environs. Many of the municipal bodies have undeveloped and / or eroded tax systems and suffer from lack of capital funds for development. The services if provided have deteriorated over the years and there seems no sign of reversal. The financial position of urban bodies is very poor, expenditure exceeds the revenue, and it is common for the deficit to be mint by the state government by giving the grant and assistance of occasions of by waivers of loans, octoroi, which was the main source of revenue, has since been abolished and now local bodies have to depend upon transfers that is grant and share from the state government. Only 10% of government expenditure is spent on maintenance of public facilities. Many steps have been taken by both the central and state government like JNNURM, Kansiram Garib Awas Yojana, Water supply, Sewerage and Solid waste disposal and road construction etc. But not surprisingly, there are conflict and controversies and sometime, it is not possible to fix their responsibilities for lapses in providing civic amenities or in solving other urban problems. Therefore, there is lack of infrastructure in small urban centers.

In the context of development, there is a need of decentralization for the healthiest urbanization. Therefore, small urban centers of country can play important role. And if there is a proper provision of urban facilities along with employment, quality education, urban amenities and social protection, which attracts the rural people, and fulfill the rural needs and also deduct the burden of big urban centers.

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